

Questionable Research Practices and Open Science in Undergraduate Empirical Projects: Results from a Nationwide Survey amongst German Psychology Students

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

questionable research practices, psychology students, research methods, open research practices

Purpose of this paper

In recent years, a substantial body of research has established that questionable research practices (QRPs) and p-hacking amongst researchers are alarmingly widespread (Banks, Rogelberg, Woznyj, Landis, & Rupp, 2016; Fiedler & Schwarz, 2016; John, Loewenstein, & Prelec, 2012). But so far, little is known about their prevalence in the student population, or coverage throughout undergraduate education. As the researchers of the future, today's students will substantially shape the scientific field of tomorrow, and therefore should be educated about sound research practices early on. However, regardless of their preferred future occupation, students have a vital interest in ensuring their education is based on reliable and open research, since such research results lay the foundation for their future professional activities (Konferenzrat der Psychologie-Fachschaften-Konferenz, 2018). Therefore, as members of the Students' Open Science Initiative of the German "Psychologie-Fachschaften-Konferenz" (SOSIP), we conducted a nationwide survey to assess the current state of teaching practices in psychology regarding QRPs and open science.

Design/methodology/approach

The final sample consisted of 1,398 psychology students and recent graduates (78% female, 20% male and 0.2% diverse, $M_{\text{age}} = 22.93$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 3.94$ years) from 58 universities. 64% were enrolled in a bachelor's and 33% in a master's program, while the remaining 3% graduated within the last three years. Participants were asked to provide data on their use of nine QRPs and two positive research practices (preregistration and power analysis) in empirical research projects throughout their studies. They further provided information on teaching coverage of specific QRPs and the general topics of the replication crisis and open science. Finally, we asked participants about their attitudes (perceived importance, interest and felt informedness) towards the topic area.

Findings

The key results indicate that the use of QRPs in students' empirical projects is prevalent, on average, in up to one third of observed projects, but appears to decrease over time: While two thirds of all participants used at least one QRPs in their first-year projects, this percentage lowers to around 50% in their bachelor's and one third in their master's theses. "No sample-planning" and "selective reporting of dependent variables" emerged as the most prevalent QRPs in 34% and 23% of observed projects, respectively. Regarding the positive research practices,

power analysis was covered in 34% of observed projects, and 23% of all projects were preregistered, e.g., using an online tool or by handing in a proposal to the lecturer directly.

Even though 75% of participants report having heard about the replication crisis and QRPs in their courses, teaching coverage was heterogeneous across universities and subject areas. These topics were mainly covered in methodology and statistics courses, where 55% of participants got in contact with them. By contrast, coverage in applied psychology courses varied between 28 % in social psychology and 4.4 % in developmental psychology.

Perceived importance of the topic area of open science and the replication was notably high, with 94% indicating high or very high importance. By contrast, participants' ratings of felt informedness on the topic were mixed: While 34% indicated a high or very high level of felt informedness, another 34% reported the opposite.

Research limitations/implications

As our survey followed a cross-sectional design, causal mechanisms underlying the usage of QRPs cannot be directly inferred from our data. The necessarily retrospective estimation of QRP usage throughout an entire study period poses a complex memory task. Therefore, it cannot be ruled out that memory effects or biases affected the participants' accounts. Likewise, some participants may have misunderstood the given definitions of QRPs, leading to inaccurate self-reports (e.g. reporting non-questionable practices as questionable and vice versa). To alleviate this problem, illustrative examples of the QRPs were provided.

Importantly, the role of QRP item phrasing should be taken into account. As noted by Fiedler & Schwarz (2016), research employing a broad QRP definition may result in higher number of reported QRPs, while a more narrow and specific definition may decrease this estimation. Since we provided, in part, specific examples alongside our QRP descriptions, this effect may have affected our results and should be considered in comparisons with other studies which used differently worded QRP items.

What is original/value of paper

To the best of our knowledge, the present study is amongst the first to assess the prevalence of QRPs in a large sample of psychology students across various study stages and project types. With this study, we aim to establish an empirical basis for further work to improve teaching practices in psychology and neighboring fields. By shedding light on students' perspectives on the open science discussion, we hope to underline the vital importance of including sound and open research practices in tertiary education.

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